

Preparing to Include? Special and Inclusive Teacher Education: From Policy Aspiration to Practice

Lisa Clinton

lisa.clinton5@mail.dcu.ie

This paper critically examines the preparedness of Student Teachers (STs) for inclusive teaching across the increasingly diverse landscape of Irish primary education, with a particular focus on the under-explored role of Placement Tutors (PTs). Using a conceptual policy analysis, the study draws on established analytical lenses to explore how inclusive education is constructed, communicated, and enacted within key national Initial Teacher Education (ITE) policy texts. The analysis identifies a strong rights-based commitment to inclusion across Irish policy, aligned with international frameworks and guidance. However, it also reveals ambiguity in how inclusive pedagogy is expected to be supported, modelled, and assessed during school placement. PTs emerge as boundary actors positioned between higher education institutions, schools, and policy expectations, with significant potential to shape STs' developing understandings of inclusive practice. The absence however, of a national framework for PT preparation or clearly defined expectations results in inconsistent enactment, uneven access to inclusive learning opportunities, and variability in feedback and assessment. The paper argues that strategically strengthening the role of PTs through structured professional development, clearer placement requirements, and stronger HEI-school partnerships is essential for realising Ireland's inclusive education ambitions. This conceptual analysis informs the next stage of research, which will explore how PTs interpret and enact inclusion in practice.

Keywords: Inclusive Education; Initial Teacher Education; Placement Tutors; School Placement; Continuing Professional Development

Highlights

- Placement Tutors (PTs) are an under-utilised resource for strengthening inclusive practice in Initial Teacher Education (ITE).
- Irish ITE policy conveys strong inclusive values but structured guidance for inclusive school placement enactment is limited.
- Equity of inclusive learning opportunities for Student Teachers remains inconsistent and is influenced by local school and partnership contexts.

Introduction

Inclusive education is broadly defined as a process of strengthening education systems to reach out to all learners, recognising diversity as a resource, and eliminating discrimination (United Nations Educational Sustainable and Cultural Organisation) (UNESCO), 2009). This definition is reflected at European level, where the European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (EASNIE) (2015) consider inclusion as the right of all learners to high-quality education meeting individual needs, preparing them for full participation in society (Pantić & Florian, 2015). This underpins recent Irish policy developments on inclusive education from the National Council for Special Education (NCSE, 2024).

Special and Inclusive education was firmly established in recent decades both nationally and internationally as a legal right. Globally, *the Salamanca Statement* (UNESCO, 1994) framed inclusion as a non-negotiable commitment, asserting that schools accommodate all children regardless of physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic, or other conditions. This was reinforced by the 2015 *United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4* (SDG4) (UNESCO, 2015), which set the agenda for 'inclusive and equitable quality education for all'. The *United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities* (UNCRPD, 2006), ratified by Ireland in 2018 (Government of Ireland, 2018), expects that persons with disabilities access a free, inclusive, and quality education equal with others in their communities. At European level, the EASNIE (2015) emphasised that high-quality teacher preparation is central to building inclusive systems. These developments positioned inclusion as a system-level reform agenda (Florian, 2019).

Influenced by these international commitments, Ireland's legislative and policy roadmap views inclusion as a core principle of educational provision and *The Education for Persons with Special Educational Needs Act* (EPSEN) (Government of Ireland, 2004) embeds this. Globally, this marked a shift toward recognising teacher quality as central to education reform. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development's (OECD) influential report *Teachers Matter* (OECD, 2005), considered teachers as the most significant in-school factor for student achievement, calling for a renewed focus on ITE, induction, and professional development (Cochran-Smith *et al.*, 2018). Against this backdrop, the establishment of the Teaching Council in 2006 initiated a process of modernising ITE programmes, culminating in *Céim* (Teaching Council, 2020), the revised regulatory standard

for all ITE providers, and the *Guidelines for School Placement* (Teaching Council, 2022). Together, they outline expectations for preparing teachers to meet the realities of modern classrooms.

Nonetheless, as international research by Florian (2015), Hick *et al.*, (2019), demonstrates, policy intentions don't necessarily translate into practice. In Ireland, the NCSE (2019; 2024) highlighted that NQTs often feel underprepared to respond to the complexities of diverse learners in classrooms. The OECD (2019; 2021) similarly stresses the importance of providing teachers with knowledge and practical skills for teaching in diverse settings, noting that the quality of practical experiences during ITE and school placement is a decisive factor in doing so (Waitoller & Artiles, 2013).

This paper illustrates the gap between inclusive aspirations and enactment. It draws on my professional experience as class teacher, deputy principal, Special Education Needs Coordinator (SENCO), Newly Qualified Teacher (NQT) mentor and, more recently, PT, where I observed variability in how inclusive practice is modelled, discussed, and assessed during placement (Pantić & Florian, 2015). This raises a central question: are teachers being adequately prepared for the realities of increasingly diverse classrooms? If not, how can ITE address this? While the Cooperating Teacher (CT) is often the most immediate influence on a ST's development, realities in many Irish schools complicate this. This inquiry explores PTs as a potentially under-utilised lever between ITE policy aspirations and classroom realities. Akkerman and Bakker (2011) describe PTs as occupying a boundary role, functioning between communities of practice and facilitating learning across institutional borders. With new special classes frequently staffed by early-career teachers and leaders still navigating evolving inclusive expectations, mentoring capacity can be uneven. In this context, the PT's role becomes increasingly significant. Positioned as the bridge between the HEI and the school, PTs engage with STs, CTs and leaders, putting them in a strong position to assess both the quality and inclusiveness of support provided. Although PTs come from varied professional backgrounds, the degree to which they prioritise inclusive pedagogy in their feedback can decisively determine how STs understand and enact inclusion.

Proposed Conceptual Framework

This research adopts a layered conceptual framework drawing on established analytical lenses. Céim (Teaching Council, 2020) is explored through Ball's Policy Cycle

(1994), which considers policy across the contexts of influence, text production and practice. The Guidelines for School Placement (Teaching Council, 2022) are analysed using Bell and Stevenson's (2015) leadership and governance model alongside Riddell's procedural justice framework (2003; 2009; 2010), highlighting issues of equity, participation and fairness in enactment. These approaches combined offer complementary insights into how Irish ITE policy prepares teachers for inclusive practice and how inclusion is conveyed in practice settings (Florian & Spratt, 2013). Kennedy's (2014) spectrum of CPD models provides a backdrop for considering how PT preparation might move beyond procedural induction towards more transformative learning.

Ethical Considerations

This paper is conceptual in nature, based on policy analysis, so no primary data involving participants was collected at this stage, and formal ethical approval was not sought. The next phase of the research will involve semi-structured interviews with PTs and the CT. This empirical stage will be conducted in line with institutional requirements and subject to approval by the Dublin City University Research Ethics Committee. This ensures compliance with ethical standards for informed consent, confidentiality, and data protection.

Analysis through Ball's Policy Cycle (1994)

Ball's Policy Cycle (1994) helps trace how inclusive education policy in ITE is shaped, articulated, and enacted. At the context of influence level, inclusion is prioritised through international drivers such as *the Salamanca Statement* (UNESCO, 1994), the *UNCRPD* (2006), and OECD (2019; 2021), calling for stronger preparation for diversity. These influences demonstrate Ireland's intent to bring ITE in line with international practice. In the context of policy text production, this ambition is formalised in *Céim* (Teaching Council, 2020) and the *Guidelines for School Placement* (2022). Both present inclusion as a core principle (Florian & Spratt, 2013), referencing *Universal Design for Learning* (UDL) (CAST, 2018) and using rights-based, progressive language. However, Irish policy analysis reveals that while *Céim* articulates inclusive values clearly, enactment and assessment structures are ambiguous, particularly around placement (Gorman and Furlong, 2023). At the context of practice level, the lived experience of school placement highlights significant variability. While inclusion is emphasised as a policy value, explicit guidance on its enactment during placement and clarity about who is responsible for embedding it, remains

limited. Consequently, feedback to STs often depends on the expertise and priorities of individual PTs or CTs, leading to uneven attention to inclusive pedagogy.

This analysis highlights persistent tensions between global and national aspirations, progressive policy texts, and uneven local enactment. The main challenge remains the ambiguity of roles and the inconsistent preparation of those guiding STs (Cochran-Smith *et al.*, 2018). Moving inclusive education from aspiration to reality demands clearer placement structures and stronger capacity. Ball's framework identifies the context of practice as the weak link in Ireland's inclusive ITE system, where support is most required. While Ball (1994) exposes practice-level limitations, Bell and Stevenson (2015) and Riddell (2009) strengthens this by demonstrating how leadership structures and procedural equity shape STs' access to inclusive opportunities.

Analysis through Bell and Stevenson (2015) combined with Riddell's Lens (2009)

While Ball's (1994) framework highlights variability at practice level, Bell and Stevenson's (2015) governance model provides clarity on responsibility and authority. Combined with Riddell's (2009) procedural justice framework, these lenses illuminate how placement policy is interpreted and enacted in ITE, emphasising responsibility, authority, and fairness in STs' access to inclusive learning opportunities.

The Guidelines for School Placement (Teaching Council, 2022) promote exposure to diverse contexts, including special classes but do not require it. As implementation lies with schools, uneven access is shaped by local ethos, leadership, and CT capacity. Furlong and Gorman (2025) talk of CTs' readiness being influenced by partnership conditions and that mentoring roles remain inconsistently defined across HEI–school contexts. This variability is further mediated by the strength of university–school partnerships. Brennan and King (2022) highlight external facilitators as critical for supporting inclusive practice. The lack of national standards for mentor or tutor preparation in inclusive pedagogy reinforces these inconsistencies. The absence of national standards for mentor and tutor preparation reinforces these inconsistencies, despite European guidance supporting structured inclusive professional learning for all educators (EASNIE, 2022). O'Sullivan and Ó Conaill (2022) found that mentoring during school placement in Ireland was uneven, shaped by informal norms, unclear role expectations and variable relational dynamics with inconsistent feedback for STs. This reveals a major equity concern: some STs experience rich, hands-on inclusive practice,

while others encounter superficial inclusion. Given that school placement accounts for 25% of undergraduate and 40% of postgraduate ITE programmes (Teaching Council, 2020), these disparities are significant. Placement is the most important and transformative learning experience of ITE (Teaching Council, 2020), yet opportunities for developing inclusive practice within such experiences remain uneven (Waitoller & Artiles, 2013).

Irish classrooms are increasingly complex. There are growing numbers of learners with additional needs, special classes and special schools (NCSE, 2024; Department of Education and Youth, 2023; OECD, 2021). Many STs are stepping into teaching contexts new to them as well as the schools themselves, who are developing their own inclusive practices. Without clearer structures, systematic mentor and tutor preparation, and equitable access to inclusive placements, inclusion remains aspirational. Strengthening placement as a bridge between policy and practice is therefore essential. Gorodetsky and Barak's (2008) concept of the "edge community" reinforces this, showing that effective partnerships develop when all engage as co-learners rather than through hierarchical, compliance-driven arrangements.

Combined, the analysis demonstrates realising inclusion in practice requires re-envisioning school placement as a structured, equitable, and professionally supported cornerstone of ITE rather than an unequal opportunity.

Analysis and Discussion

This policy analysis highlights a clear rhetorical and structural commitment to inclusion within Irish ITE. *Céim* (Teaching Council, 2020) embeds inclusion as a statutory requirement and references *Universal Design for Learning* (UDL) as a guiding approach for supporting learner variability from the outset. The *Guidelines for School Placement* (Teaching Council, 2022) promote but do not mandate exposure to a range of school contexts, including special classes and special schools. The subsequent *Initial Teacher Education Policy Statement* (Department of Education and Youth, 2023) further specifies that inclusive competencies should be explicitly assessed in inclusive diverse placement contexts. Applying Ball's context of practice lens reveals concerning gaps. While inclusion is emphasised in all documents, explicit guidance as to how PTs should support STs in developing inclusive teaching practices remains unclear. Currently there is no national requirement for PTs to have experience or specific training in inclusive pedagogy,

differentiation, or UDL. Consequently, the degree to which inclusive teaching is discussed, and assessed by PTs varies widely between placements (Sharma *et al.*, 2014).

PTs with prior SENCO or special school experience may offer targeted feedback on teaching strategies for STs working in a special class setting or a mainstream class with multiple pupils requiring individualised support. In other cases, PTs with no formal training in inclusive education may focus primarily on general classroom management and curriculum coverage, leaving inclusive pedagogy potentially unaddressed. As Walton and Rusznyak (2013) note, in special class contexts, underlying pedagogical reasoning behind differentiation and adaptive instruction is clearer, offering quality learning opportunities for STs. These can be missed however, without guided, quality supervision from PTs. This highlights how PTs' expertise may influence placement feedback (Teaching Council, 2020).

The varied backgrounds of PTs, from retired teachers to mid-career practitioners and academic specialists, results in inconsistent practices. Most receive basic induction, and there is no national standard for preparation in inclusive education. Consequently, the depth and focus of feedback provided to STs, particularly those placed in special classes or in mainstream classrooms with prominent levels of need, depends on the individual PTs' background experience rather than a consistent framework. International evidence reinforces mentor preparation importance. Sharma *et al.*, (2014) revealed how mentors trained in inclusive pedagogy were more likely to engage STs in reflective conversations about diversity, whereas those without training tended to focus on narrower, technical aspects of teaching. Similarly, Florian and Beaton (2023) argue that inclusive practice is most effectively developed when enshrined in routine planning, observation, and feedback cycles and not treated as an optional topic.

While the CT is naturally the most immediate and influential figure in shaping a ST's practice, realities in many Irish schools today complicate this dynamic. New special classes are opening at pace, frequently staffed by early-career teachers, while school leaders themselves are also navigating their roles in supporting inclusive education. In these evolving contexts, the role of the PTs becomes even more critical, not only in supporting the STs directly but also in shaping how inclusive pedagogy is prioritised in feedback and assessment. Developing inclusive practice demands what Edwards (2005) calls relational agency (the capacity to recognise, access and work with the expertise of others) which further highlights

the need for PTs to be equipped to model and support collaborative teaching and learning approaches.

Although PTs may bring subject-specific or academic expertise that shapes their overall appraisal, I argue this expertise should be underpinned by a strong understanding of learner variability and inclusive pedagogy. These principles are not confined to specific subjects or settings. They are central to effective teaching in every classroom. Without this foundation, PTs risk reinforcing narrow interpretations of ‘good teaching’ that overlook the complex, diverse realities STs are encountering, particularly in special classes or high-need mainstream contexts. A deep grasp of inclusive pedagogy enables PTs to identify and guide adaptive strategies, differentiate feedback meaningfully, supporting the development of STs to plan for all learners. In both mainstream and special class contexts, this knowledge is imperative for meaningful support and professional learning for STs. Where in-school mentoring is inconsistent or underdeveloped, the PT’s role in translating inclusive theory into practice becomes particularly important. Cuenca (2010) cautions that, without explicit training PTs often adopt an *in loco paedagogus* stance, reproducing their own preferred teaching habits than applying broader pedagogical principles. When PTs’ experiences are limited inclusion can be sidelined.

From an equity perspective, Riddell’s lens highlights a risk: without structured systems providing access to inclusive experiences, STs’ preparation depends as much on luck (who assesses them, where they are placed) as on the ITE curriculum. This variability is also mediated by the quality of partnerships, which Brennan and King (2022) argue are central to enacting inclusion. Ensuring that PTs are equipped and expected to foster inclusive pedagogy mitigates this inequity and strengthens alignment between policy aspirations and practice.

Limitations

This paper represents an early, conceptual stage of the research. Although grounded in policy analysis and existing literature, it does not yet draw on empirical data, so conclusions about the impact of PT-focused interventions remain tentative. The analysis is situated within the Irish context, limiting transferability to systems with different ITE structures. Nonetheless, the conceptual framework and identified gaps are likely relevant to others navigating similar policy–practice tensions.

Research Agenda and Implications

This paper argues that PTs hold a significant, overlooked role in realising Ireland's inclusive education ambitions in ITE, echoing concerns about inconsistent enactment of *Céim* (Gorman and Furlong, 2023). While policies such as *Céim*, the *Guidelines for School Placement*, and the *Initial Teacher Education Policy Statement* articulate inclusive values, their enactment in school placements remains inconsistent. Identifying PTs as a lever for bridging the theory-practice gap, opens a research pathway that informs national frameworks for PTs training, role definition, and integration into HEI-school partnership strategies.

The next phase will employ semi-structured interviews with PTs and CTs, alongside document analysis of placement feedback, to examine how inclusive pedagogy is prioritised and assessed. This inquiry will explore PTs' interpretations of their role in supporting inclusion, how inclusive pedagogy is reflected in placement feedback and assessment, and the CPD needs of tutors (Waitoller & Artiles, 2013; Sharma *et al.*, 2014).

Four central questions guide this next stage:

1. How do PTs interpret their role in supporting inclusive teaching?
2. To what extent is inclusion observed, discussed, or evaluated in placement feedback?
3. What factors influence the consistency and quality of this support?
4. What CPD opportunities exist or are required to strengthen PTs' capacity to support student teachers in inclusive contexts?

Addressing these questions requires attention to structural and cultural dimensions of ITE. The consistency of inclusive support is shaped by HEI frameworks, school leadership, co-operating teacher expertise, and relational dynamics between universities and schools. Brennan and King's (2022) study of professional learning communities, built in part on school–university partnerships, demonstrates how collaborative structures sustain inclusive practice over time, where formal links between schools and higher education are absent. In the Irish context while *Céim* makes a strong rhetorical commitment to inclusion, its policy language has been critiqued for obscuring how such commitments are enacted (Gorman & Furlong, 2023), and concerns remain about the consistency of inclusion in practice across schools (Hick *et al.*, 2019; NCSE, 2024).

The identification of PTs' professional learning needs is critical. Current preparation is ad hoc and transmissive, focusing on procedural induction rather than deeper professional growth. This risks limiting PTs to technical rather than pedagogical support for STs. Kennedy's (2014) spectrum of CPD models highlights moving beyond compliance-driven training towards dialogic and transformative approaches. Applying this framework to PT preparation emphasises the need for practice-based, reflective CPD with a clear focus on inclusive pedagogy.

The implications carry beyond the PTs' role itself. By clarifying and strengthening PTs' inclusive functions, HEIs reinforce their partnerships with schools, ensure greater equity in placement experiences, and build inclusive pedagogy reliably across the ITE continuum. Ball's (1994) Context of Practice reminds us that policy breathes in settings shaped by capacity, relationships, and local structures. The move toward mandatory SEN placements is timely (DEY, 2024), but risks exposing current gaps in preparation, professional development, and role clarity. National frameworks defining expectations, supporting mentors and tutors that embed accountability are imperative.

Conclusion

This paper argues that PTs hold an important but under-recognised role in bridging the gap between policy aspiration and classroom enactment in inclusive education. Although Irish and international frameworks including Céim (Teaching Council, 2020), the Guidelines for School Placement (Teaching Council, 2022), and the Initial Teacher Education Policy Statement (Department of Education and Youth, 2023) articulate strong commitments to inclusion, the reality of placement remains uneven. Positioned at the junction of policy, HEI expectations, and school practice, PTs are uniquely positioned to shape how inclusive pedagogy is modelled, discussed, and assessed.

Their potential currently remains underdeveloped. Reliance on goodwill, local ethos, or patchy implementation creates inequities across inclusive experiences encountered by STs. Clarifying the expectations of PTs, embedding inclusive pedagogy explicitly into placement structures, and providing sustained, transformative CPD (Kennedy, 2014), ensures that PTs are prepared drive inclusive practice by transforming policy intentions into classroom practice. Variability in PT capacity and placement quality leaves inclusive preparation dependent on chance, undermining Ireland's wider equity commitments. Addressing these

gaps is vital to strengthen ITE and ensure future teachers deliver on inclusive education, as a legal entitlement and a lived classroom reality (Hick et al., 2019; OECD, 2021).

References

- Akkerman, S. and Bakker, A. 2011. Boundary crossing and boundary objects. *Review of Educational Research*, 81(2), pp. 132–169.
- Ball, S.J. 1994. *Education reform: A critical and post-structural approach*. Buckingham: Open University Press.
- Bell, L. and Stevenson, H. 2015. *Education policy: Process, themes and impact*. London: Routledge.
- Brennan, A. and King, F. 2022. Teachers' experiences of transformative professional learning to narrow the values–practice gap related to inclusive practice. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 52(2), pp. 175–193. doi: 10.1080/0305764X.2021.1965092.
- CAST. 2018. *Universal design for learning guidelines version 2.2*. CAST. Available at: <http://udlguidelines.cast.org> (Accessed: 21 August 2025).
- Cochran-Smith, M., Ell, F., Ludlow, L., Grudnoff, L. and Aitken, G. 2018. Initial teacher education: What does it take to put equity at the centre? *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 74, pp. 9–20. doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2018.04.022.
- Cuenca, A. 2010. In loco paedagogus: The pedagogy of a novice university supervisor. *Teaching Education*, 21(1), pp. 7–21.
- Department of Education and Youth. 2023. *Initial Teacher Education Policy Statement*. Dublin: Government of Ireland.
- Department of Education and Youth. 2024. *Initial Teacher Education: Inclusion of Placements in Special Education Settings – Circular Letter*. Dublin: Government of Ireland.
- European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education. 2015. *Empowering teachers to promote inclusive education: Literature review*. Odense: European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education. Available at: <https://www.european-agency.org/resources/publications/empowering-teachers-promote-inclusive-education> (Accessed: 25 August 2025).
- European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education. 2022. *Profile for inclusive teacher professional learning: Including all education professionals in teacher professional learning for inclusion*. Odense: European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education. Available at: <https://www.european-agency.org/resources/publications/TPL4I-profile> (Accessed: 25 August 2025).
- Edwards, A. 2005. Relational agency: Learning to be a resourceful practitioner. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 43(3), pp. 168–182.
- Florian, L. 2015. Inclusive pedagogy: A transformative approach to individual differences but can it help reduce educational inequalities? *Scottish Educational Review*, 47(1), pp. 5–14.
- Florian, L. 2019. On the necessary co-existence of special and inclusive education. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 23(7–8), pp. 691–704. doi:10.1080/13603116.2019.1622801.

- Florian, L. and Beaton, M.C. 2023. Inclusive pedagogy in teacher education: Theory, policy and practice. In: S. Miles and N. Singal (eds.) *Education and disability in the global south: New perspectives*. London: Bloomsbury, pp. 145–162.
- Florian, L. and Spratt, J. 2013. Enacting inclusion: A framework for interrogating inclusive practice. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 28(2), pp. 119–135. doi:10.1080/08856257.2013.778111.
- Furlong, C. and Gorman, A. 2025. Exploring how the experiential narratives of cooperating teachers impact their role in supporting student teachers on school placement. *Teaching Education*, pp. 1–17. doi: 10.1080/10476210.2025.2525166.
- Gorodetsky, M. and Barak, J. 2008. The educational-cultural edge: A participatory learning environment for co-emergence of personal and institutional growth. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 24(8), pp. 1907–1918.
- Government of Ireland. 2004. *Education for Persons with Special Educational Needs Act 2004 (EPSEN Act)*. Available at: <http://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2004/act/30/enacted/en/html> (Accessed: 25 August 2025).
- Government of Ireland. 2018. *Ireland ratifies the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities*. Available at: <https://www.gov.ie/en/press-release/aa312-government-announces-decision-to-accede-to-the-optional-protocol-to-the-un-convention-on-the-rights-of-persons-with-disabilities/> (Accessed: 25 August 2025).
- Hick, P., Matziari, A., Mintz, J., Ó Murchú, F., Cahill, K., Hall, K., Curtin, C. and Solomon, Y. 2019. *Initial teacher education for inclusion: Final report to the National Council for Special Education*. NCSE Research Report No. 27. Trim: National Council for Special Education.
- Kennedy, A. 2014. Models of continuing professional development: A framework for analysis. *Professional Development in Education*, 40(3), pp. 336–351. doi:10.1080/19415257.2014.929293.
- National Council for Special Education. 2019. *Policy advice on teacher education for inclusion*. Trim: National Council for Special Education. Available at: <https://ncse.ie/publications> (Accessed: 25 August 2025).
- National Council for Special Education. 2024. *Policy advice on special education provision in Ireland*. Trim: National Council for Special Education. Available at: https://ncse.ie/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Policy_Advice_Special_Education_Provision_Ireland.pdf (Accessed: 25 August 2025).
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. 2005. *Teachers matter: Attracting, developing, and retaining effective teachers*. Paris: OECD Publishing.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. 2019. *TALIS 2018 results (Volume II): Teachers and school leaders as valued professionals*. Paris: OECD Publishing.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. 2021. *Strengthening the impact of education research*. Paris: OECD Publishing.

- O'Sullivan, R. and Ó Conaill, E. 2022. Mentoring on school placement: Dialogic tensions and uneven practices in Initial Teacher Education. *Irish Educational Studies*, 41(3), pp. 367–384.
- Pantić, N. and Florian, L. 2015. Developing teachers as agents of inclusion and social justice. *Education Inquiry*, 6(3), pp. 333–351. doi:10.3402/edui.v6.27311.
- Riddell, S. 2003. Procedural justice and special educational needs assessments in England and Scotland. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 7(3), pp. 201–222. doi:10.1080/1360311032000070812.
- Riddell, S. 2009. Social justice, equality and inclusion in Scottish education. *Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education*, 30(3), pp. 283–296. doi:10.1080/01596300903037096.
- Riddell, S. 2010. Equity, equality, and justice in education: International perspectives. In: M. Arnot and J.A. Dillabough (eds.) *Educating the gendered citizen: Sociological engagements with national and global agendas*. London: Routledge, pp. 65–83.
- Sharma, U., Forlin, C. and Loreman, T. 2014. A system-wide professional learning approach about inclusion for teachers in Hong Kong. *Asia Pacific Journal of Teacher Education*, 42(3), pp. 247–260.
- Teaching Council. 2020. *Céim: Standards for initial teacher education*. Maynooth: The Teaching Council.
- Teaching Council. 2022. *Guidelines for school placement*. Maynooth: The Teaching Council.
- United Nations. 2006. *Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities*. New York: United Nations. Available at: <https://www.un.org/disabilities/documents/convention/convoptprot-e.pdf> (Accessed: 20 July 2025).
- UNESCO. 1994. *The Salamanca statement and framework for action on special needs education*. Salamanca: UNESCO. Available at: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000098427> (Accessed: 25 August 2025).
- UNESCO. 2009. *Policy guidelines on inclusion in education*. Paris: UNESCO. Available at: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000177849> (Accessed: 12 August 2025).
- UNESCO. 2015. *Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 4): Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all*. Paris: UNESCO. Available at: <https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal4> (Accessed: 26 June 2025).
- Waitoller, F.R. and Artiles, A.J. 2013. A decade of professional development research for inclusive education: A critical review and notes for a research program. *Review of Educational Research*, 83(3), pp. 319–356. doi:10.3102/0034654313483905.
- Walton, E. and Rusznyak, L. 2013. Learning from experience: School placements for inclusive education. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 33(5), pp. 484–493.